

INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF PHARMACEUTICAL RESEARCH

INCIDENCE OF ADVERSE DRUG REACTIONS IN GERIATRIC PATIENTS IN A TERTIARY CARE HOSPITAL

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ARTICLE INFO

Article history

Received 25/11/2017

Available online

06/12/2017

Keywords

Adverse Drug Reaction;

Causality;

Preventability;

Geriatric Patients.

ABSTRACT

Drugs offer great benefit to elderly patients, but they may result in great risks when not administered or managed properly and also due to pharmacodynamics and pharmacokinetic changes. To estimate the incidence of ADR among elderly population and also to monitor the causality, preventability and severity of ADRs. The study was a prospective observational study carried out in a tertiary care hospital. The pertinent information was collected from patient IP files using a standard case record form and by enquiring about OTC medications and other drugs taken by them. All data were analyzed with the help of SPSS version 16 software. Out of 320 patients (55 had ADR) incidence of the ADRs was found to be 17.18 %. Majority of ADRs were type A reactions (50.90 %). Chi-square test was used for analysis and p value less than or equal to 0.05 was considered as significant. The study concluded by stating that involving clinical pharmacist services in patient care can significantly help to identify, resolve, and prevent the drug related problems in hospital thereby enhancing the patient outcomes.

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Please cite this article in press as **Neena Baby et al.** Incidence of Adverse Drug Reactions in Geriatric Patients in A Tertiary Care Hospital. *Indo American Journal of Pharmaceutical Research*.2017;7(11).

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INTRODUCTION

Drugs offer great benefit to elderly patients, but they may result in great risks when not administered or managed properly and also due to pharmacodynamics and pharmacokinetic changes. The World Health Organization defines an ADVERSE DRUG REACTION [ADR] as “a response to a drug which is noxious and unintended, and which occurs at doses normally used in man for the prophylaxis, diagnosis, or therapy of disease, or for the modification of physiological function [1].

ADRs may occur following a single dose, prolonged administration of a drug or results from a combination of two or more drugs. ADRs can be classified into 2 main types: Type A or Type B [2]. Type A refers to the ADRs that are expected from the pharmacological properties of a drug. These adverse effects often occur in patients who are unusually sensitive to the known pharmacological properties of the drug. They are largely dose dependent and uncommon in normal doses [3, 4]. Type B reactions are the unexpected responses that are not related to the drug's pharmacological effect. They are often immunologically mediated. This type of ADRs is much less common than type A reactions, and is generally more serious in nature [5].

Apart from type A and B, type C and D reactions have also been described [3, 4]. Type C refers to the adverse effects associated with long-term therapy, such as analgesic nephropathy; whereas type D is the delayed side effects, such as carcinogenicity or teratogenesis [3]. More than 80% of ADRs occurring in hospitals or that result in hospital admissions are Type A in nature [3, 4]. ADRs in older people are a common cause of admission to a hospital, and are an important cause of morbidity and death. Elderly patients are more prone and vulnerable to drug related reactions than younger population. Whether the advancing age is a cause of increased risk of ADR is debatable, but the specific physiological changes associated with aging certainly play a crucial role in ADRs. Reduction in hepatic metabolism and renal excretion of medications in the elderly predispose patients to drug accumulation and toxicities [8, 9]. Older individuals have an increased incidence of chronic illnesses, such as hypertension, coronary artery disease, diabetes, arthritis etc, which are often treated with multiple medication (polypharmacy) which in turn may lead to harmful drug interactions and ADRs.

Changes in pharmacokinetic and pharmacodynamic characteristics play a critical role in the increased risk of ADRs in the elderly. The most clinically significant change with aging is perhaps the decline in renal function. Decline in both the glomerular filtration rate and renal clearance of drugs about 50% occur between the age of 25 to 85[10]. Chronic illnesses in the elderly, such as hypertension and diabetes, also adversely affect renal function [9].

Elderly patients tend to have a number of chronic clinical conditions, which are often managed by polypharmacy. Although 10% of the general population take more than one prescribed medication, the incidence of polypharmacy in the elderly is far greater. A review on several studies indicates that patient aged 65 years and older use an average of 2-6 prescribed medications concurrently. Inappropriate prescribing, a potentially preventable risk factor for ADRs, occurs more often than most people could imagine. This may be because prescribed medications were found to be inappropriate, and were associated with increased risk of at least one acute hospitalization, after adjustment for age, sex, education, co-morbidity, dependency in activities of daily living and smoking. Inappropriate prescriptions of medications have also been identified in other settings, such as elderly patients undergoing ambulatory care. A BEERS criterion is used to assess inappropriate prescribing in elderly.

AIM AND OBJECTIVE:

The aim and objective of this study was to estimate the incidence of ADR among elderly population and also to monitor the causality, preventability and severity of ADRs.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

The prospective observational study was carried out in a tertiary care hospital to assess the incidence, causality, preventability and severity of ADRs. The pertinent information were collected from patient IP files using a standard case record form and by enquiring about OTC medications and other drugs taken by them. An ethical committee clearance of the institution was obtained for the study. The study was conducted over a period of six months in which 320 patients were admitted under the geriatrics department. All patients above 65 years of age were included and Psychiatry and palliative care were excluded. All data were analyzed with the help of SPSS version 16 software. Chi-square test was used for analysis and p value less than or equal to 0.05 was considered as significant.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

Among 320 patients in the study, 55 patients had ADRs. The incidence of the ADR was found to be 17.18%.

Among the 55 cases, 60% (33) were male and 40% (22) were female patients (Fig No.1) which was found similar to study conducted by Ramanath K.V. *et al* [11]. Assessment of ADRs was done using Hartwig's scale, WHO causality assessment scale and Shumock and Thronton preventability criteria (Table No. 1). In our study majority of the cases were moderate 43.63% (24). Based on WHO-UMC causality assessment scale Probable/Likely was 58.18% (32). Almost 87% of ADRs were preventable based on Schumock and Throntons preventability scale. A study conducted by Rima Shah *et al.*, had the similar findings [12].

Type A reactions were found to be 50.90% (28) (Fig No 2). A study performed by P A Routledge *et al.*, inferred that elderly patients have an increased risk of Type A reactions and many of these are avoidable [13]. Looking upon the duration of ADRs, 60% (33) of them lasted for 2-7 days and while analysing the onset of ADRs 37 of cases were ≤ 1 day (Table no. 2).

Categorizations of patients within group based on polypharmacy shows majority of cases were prescribed more than 7-10 drugs (Table No.3). Bilal Ahmed *et al.*, in Karachi and a study conducted in CMC vellore in the year 2015 also gave out similar results [14].

While managing ADR majority of patient required interventions, out of which 9% even required shifting to ICU and required dialysis. Management of Adverse drug reactions are detailed in Table (Table .no. 4), In 20 (36.36%) patients the drug was stopped and observed, 12 (21.82%) patients required invasions, for 10 (18.18%) patients drug was stopped and alternative treatment was given, 5 (9.09%) patients were shifted to ICU, for 4 (7.27%) patients the dose was reduced and administered the same drug, for 2 (3.64%) patients dialysis was required and 2 (3.64%) patients continued the same drug.

Fig No.1 Gender Distribution.

Table No 1: Assessment of ADRS.

Severity Assessment [Hartwig's scale]		Causality Assessment [WHO-UMC scale]		Preventability criteria [Shumock and Thornton scale]	
Category	No of ADR (n=55)	Category	No of ADR (n=55)	Category	No of ADR (n=55)
Mild	15	Certain	17	Definitely Preventable	48
Moderate	24	Probable/likely	32	Probably preventable	1
Severe	16	Possible	6	Not preventable	6

Fig No 2: Type of ADRS.

Table no. 2: Categorization of patients with in group based on their onset and duration of ADR.

Days	Onset of adr		Duration of adr	
	No. Of cases	%	No. Of cases	%
≤ 1 day	37	67.27	6	10.99
2-7 days	15	27.27	33	60
8-30 days	3	5.46	15	27.27
continuing	-	-	1	1.82

Table No.3: Categorization of patient within group based on polypharmacy.

Number of Drugs	Number of Patients (n =55)	Percentage (%)
1-3 drugs	8	14.55%
4-6 drugs	12	21.82%
7-10 drugs	17	30.91%
>10 drugs	18	32.72%

Table .no. 4: Management of Adverse Drug Reactions.

Category	Number of Patients	Percentage(%)
Drug stopped and observed	20	36.36
Drug stopped and given alternative	10	18.18
Dose reduced	4	7.27
Drug continue	2	3.64
Required invasions	12	21.82
ICU	5	9.09
Dialysis	2	3.64

Table 5: Association between Type of ADR And Duration of ADR ChiSquare Test.

	Value	Df	Asymp.Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	24.311a*	6	0.000
Likelihood Ratio	23.702	6	0.001
Linear-by-Linear Association	0.324	1	0.569
N of Valid Cases	55		
P ≤ 0.05 considered as significant			

*a - 8 cells (66.7%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .22.

CONCLUSION

Detecting and predicting ADRs in older people is based on monitoring and regular review of prescribed and over the counter medicines. This study shows importance in rationalizing drug therapy and to reduce the maximum amount of drugs prescribed. It will be prudent to say that timely diagnosis of ADR in geriatrics will remain a challenge for the diagnostic skills of even the most experienced clinician. The study concluded by stating that involving clinical pharmacist services in patients care can significantly help to identify, resolve, and prevent the drug related problems in hospital thereby enhancing the patient outcomes.

Developing and maintaining electronic documentation of patient medical records may serve as a valuable tool to detect early signals of potential ADRs. There is a need for future research in this area, not only for development in prevention of ADRs, but also in implementation of strategies into hospital health care system.

ABBREVIATIONS:

ADR: Adverse Drug Reaction

OTC: Over the counter

SPSS: Statistical Package for the Social Science

WHO: World Health Organization

UMC: Uppsala Monitoring Centre

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT:

We heart fully thank Dr. Alwin Thilak Christopher and Dr. Arun Pandiyan S for their valuable guidance and immense support all throughout the project. We would also like to express our humble gratitude and respect to our principal, Project Guide, staff members, management and who directly and indirectly support for the successful completion of this work.

Conflicts of Interest:

The authors have no conflicts of interest to disclose.

Funding source:

There were no funding sources included in this study.

REFERENCE

1. Karch FE, Lasagna L. Adverse drug reaction: a critical review. JAMA 1975; 234:1236-1241.
2. Rawlins MD. Adverse drug reactions. BMJ 1981; 282: 974-976.
3. Rawlins MD, Thompson JP. Pathogenesis of adverse drug reactions. Ed Davies DM. Oxford: Oxford university press, 1977; 444:446-460.
4. Park BK, Coleman JW. The immunological basis of adverse drug reactions; a report on a symposium held in Liverpool on 6th April 1988. Br J of Clinical Pharmacol 1988; 26:491-495.
5. Bowman L, Carlstedt BC, Hancock EF. Adverse drug reaction (ADR) occurrence and evaluation in elderly inpatients. Pharmacoepidemiol and Drug Saf. 1996; 5: 9-18.
6. Wiffen P, Gill M, Edwards J. Adverse drug reaction in hospital patients, Bandolier Extra 2002; 1-15.
7. Suh DC, Woodall BS, Shin SK. Clinical and economic impact of adverse drug reaction in hospitalized patients. Ann Pharmacother 2000; 34: 1373-1379.
8. Lamy P. Comparative pharmacokinetic changes and drug therapy in an older population. J Am Geriatr Soc 1982; 30(11 Suppl):S11-9.
9. Cutka DS, Evans JM, Fleming KC. Drug prescribing for elderly patients. Mayo Clinic Proc 1995; 70: 685-693.
10. Rowe JW, Andres R, Tobin JD. The effect of age on creatinine clearance in man: cross sectional and longitudinal study. J Gerontol. 1976; 31:155-16.
11. Ramanath KV, MM Prabhu, Krishnadas Nandhakumar and K Sreedhara R Pai. Monitoring of adverse reactions in geriatric south Indian patients in a tertiary care teaching hospital: A prospective study. 2016 Jan-Feb RJPBCS 1381-1387.
12. Rima Shah, Bharath Gajjar, Sagun Desai. A profile of adverse drug reactions with risk factors among geriatric patients in a tertiary care hospital in India. Nat J Physiol Pharm Pharmacol 2012; vol 2(2).
13. P.A. Routledge, M.S. O'Mahony and K.W. Woodhouse. Adverse drug reactions in elderly patients. Br J Clin Pharmacol 2003; 57(2):121-126.
14. Bilal Ahmed, Kashmira Nanji, Rakshinda Mujeeb, Muhammed Junaid Patel. Effects of polypharmacy on adverse drug reactions among geriatric outpatients at a tertiary care hospital in Karachi: A prospective cohort study. www.plosone.org. 2014 Nov, vol. 9, issue. 11.

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